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MAGNETISM CONTROLS – CLIMATE

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ABSTRACT

It is physically impossible for the miniscule gas, Carbon Dioxide with an Atomic Weight of 44, to influence the Earth's orbital position in space.

The knowledge of magnetism has always been a wonder of the ancient world ever since it was realized that a lodestone pointed in the same direction. In modern times, particularly since 2014 when NASA determined that the face of the Moon has a positive magnetic charge, towards the Earth, it is now perfectly clear why the Moon oscillates continuously between the two magnetic poles of Earth, is because the Moon's orbital pattern is in relation to the Earth, is a reflection on a larger scale of how the Earth is controlled within the Sun's Heliosphere. With this variation happening regularly over time, is somewhat like the action of a pendulum, with this constant changing influence of how the Earth's oceans tides react to the varying magnetic pulses from the Moon and of the dramatic difference between the tidal variations of the Earth's Northern Hemisphere as compared to the Southern Hemisphere. Of course, exactly the same thing occurs with the Earth's land mass although being relatively inelastic is not as evident as it is with the oceans of Earth.

Keywords:

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Moon is continually pushed backward and forward between the magnetic poles of Earth is held in place by the greater magnetic force of the Earth's Magnetosphere. The Moon shows the same face to the Earth because this face has a positive magnetic polarity which responds to the Earth's greater magnetic emission, and as it is held in this –Push and Push, sway pattern of the Earth, where it describes a regular oscillation that displays a similar characteristic as does the Earth with its spiral orbit controlled likewise by the Sun's greater Heliosphere.

This address below shows how this assumption about magnetism, is true? A simple experiment with multiple magnets demonstrates it clearly. < <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q2kHoalqO4&feature=youtu.be>>

I came to question part of Fleming’s Right Hand Rule of Magnetic Flow because in this easily-repeatable experiment, the rolling button magnet does not continue rolling to the opposing pole, but rolls into and near to the mid-section of these permanent bar magnets, which are held between each other by their respective magnetic attraction and the rolling button magnet is either attracted to a higher magnetic potential pole of the bar magnet. I’ve found that whereas conventional wisdom decrees that a magnet will always reflect the standard illustration of a magnetic field (based, no doubt, on the long-recognised ‘iron filings’ experiment), the reality is as shown in this simple experiment, namely that there is a compression point in the centre, having a higher magnetic potential but also with a high potential to do work. I should add that I’ve conducted the ‘iron filings’ experiment, but on a very large scale, and this experiment also confirms the presence of a central magnetic pressure point, outside the normal. Unfortunately, because years ago no-one seems to have conducted the ‘iron filings’ experiment on this large scale, the presence of the mid-field pressure point has been missed, so that this has resulted in all of our scientific textbooks showing this erroneous omission, with the further result that all assumptions of the future shape of such things as the Earth’s Magnetosphere, the Sun’s Heliosphere, etc., are all reflecting this error. To further confirm this, I’ve found applying a Gauss Meter, that this central portion of a permanent magnet has a higher internal Gauss value than that of either of the poles.(1).

1. **Figure 1:** Showing the increased Gauss Readings within the central portion of this Permanent Magnet.

It follows from this simple experiment shown in Figure 1, above that this central compression point that the imagined shape of the Earth’s (and indeed the Moon, and the Sun, etc.) Magnetosphere has been misinterpreted in conventional thinking and is illustrated constantly as being likened as a ‘rugby football’ shaped, whereas in reality it should be shown to be rather like a ‘peanut’ shape, with a compression point near its middle. This is a vital point, because once this is realised then a number of factors can be related to the Earth’s Magnetosphere begin to make sense, such as why is it that the Earth’s tropical weather patterns are so different to those away from the Tropics, and why is it that the Tropospheric winds and the Jet Streams are always

constantly moving away from the Equator? Is because Earth's atmosphere is subjected to the increased magnetic pressure within the Equator zone.

Again, when this "peanut shape" is recognised, it makes sense as to why that the much smaller Moon is held in its position in relation to the Northern Hemisphere of the Earth being closer to the Earth, some 365,395 Kilometres, whereas with the Southern Hemisphere it is further away, some 406,750 Kilometers. Thus, the Moon oscillates under the influence of the Earth's northern magnetic emission to a greater degree, being basically, negative, and so this constant magnetic interaction explains why there is a much greater tidal influence in the Northern Hemisphere, some 15 meters as distinct to the Southern Hemisphere, some 1.8 meters for the same latitude.

The Moon's gravitational (Gm) value is 1.66m/s/s, while at both latitudes 45° North and 45° South of the Earth's Equator, the Ge value is 9.80665m/s/s. This underscores my argument in the previous paragraph: when the Moon is at 'Full Moon' this is why the tides at 45° of northern latitude of the oceans can rise and fall 15 meters, while at the same time within the Southern Hemisphere it might be only 1.8 meters. To explain such consistent differences there has to be an external force acting upon the ocean surfaces, and its reason is to me that it is the magnetic influence of the Moon with its constant but oscillating face to the Earth.

Further by the fact that the Moon is always closer to the Earth in the Northern Hemisphere (at 356,395 kilometers - 2008) as compared to the Southern Hemisphere (406,750 kilometers - 2008), and that its relationship in the Northern Hemisphere to the Earth's Equator magnetic reaction is at an angle of 15°33'28" compared to only 12°56'17" when within the Southern Hemisphere. Thus, a full moon is viewed always within the Northern Hemisphere, and appears never as "big" as it is when viewed from the Southern Hemisphere.

However, these figures reflect the measurements at that particular time, because the reality is that the Moon's orbit in respect of the Earth is spirally, elliptical rather than the circular image that is generally assumed. This is my unconventional view! The Earth's orbit around the Sun has a similarly spiral elliptical orbital pattern, something that has been recognised for a long time now. And why would that be? I contend that both orbits are controlled by exactly the same phenomenon: the interplay between magnetic forces that cause constant oscillations. Thus, as the Earth follows its orbit around the Sun once an Earth Year, so also does the Moon once a Lunar Month. And because of the constantly changing relationship between the two, they describe a continuous pattern that resembles an Archimedes's Screw motion, combined with the stretching and contracting of the distances between the two bodies (with exactly the same pattern demonstrated by the Earth in its relationship to the Sun), and it is these changes that are the real controlling factors in our weather patterns here on Earth.

Further, there are the now well-recognised magnetic shifts of the Sun's Heliosphere whereby the Sun's magnetic field appears to reverse approximately every eleven years (the Schwab Cycles). I say "appears" advisedly, because, could it be that we have all been fooled into thinking that this is, and that what really happens is that we on Earth are merely part of that same "Archimedes's Screw" in our relationship with the Sun? Could it be that as our position in Space is constantly changing in the manner outlined, that the reality is that the Sun's magnetic field has not, in fact,

changed, but that our perception of it has changed, because our observation position in Space has changed?10

The rate of change of momentum of a moving body, in this case both the Earth and the Moon, is proportional to the outside magnetic force acting on its magnetic field in the same direction; so also it is with the Sun's Heliosphere. (This argument is in agreement with Einstein's 2nd Law of Motion.) It is this overall oscillating effect that determines the slow change of direction of the spiral elliptical orbit of Earth (and of the Moon, and of the Sun) in accordance with "Kepler's Law". There is a further magnetic factor that should be considered here, specifically that I've long-contended that a magnetic field is not a matter of a simple 'plus' and 'minus' charge, but rather it consists of a pattern of four changes as demonstrated by that well-recognised phenomenon – the sine wave, viz: Positive/positive(+,+), Positive/negative(+,-), Negative/negative(-,-), and Negative/positive(-,+). Thus, the Sun's much more powerful Heliosphere in its relationship to the Earth's Magnetosphere (and similarly with the Moon's magnetic field) are directly controlled with these four magnetic Influences(2); and it is a 'sine wave' effect that determines the Earth's orbital pattern, as a result, our seasons.

There is another factor which needs to be considered here, and this is a phenomenon about which most people are blissfully unaware: namely that the South Pole of a magnet is always stronger than the North Pole! Refer back to Figure 1, (As an historical footnote, it is worth pointing out that all our magnetic compasses traditionally have needles that point North. Reality is that the needles – being little magnets themselves - actually point South towards the stronger pole, but tradition holds the opposite, simple because the discovery of magnetism – via the lodestone – occurred to people within the Northern Hemisphere before the effective discovery of the Southern Hemisphere. And so the 'pointy' end of the needles when they are made are actually has a 'north' polarity part of the needle magnet that forms because the 'sharp' end that is the reality, the south pole of the needle that is attracted from the greater up potential magnetic potential from the Earth's Magnetosphere (pressure) South Pole. Confused? No, it's simple really – think about the reality from which you are currently standing or sitting!

These magnetic forces are continuously at work within the Earth (and the other heavenly bodies) all must be one of the factors that have led to the now-recognised 'Continental Drift' theory. One has only to consider that there has been a gradual shift in land mass towards the Northern Hemisphere. Could this be because of the influence of the push of the stronger positive magnetic force from the Southern Hemisphere towards a lower magnetic potential force of the Northern Hemisphere? It is certainly demonstrated in the distinctively stronger oceanic tidal movements between the Northern Hemisphere as distinct to the Southern Hemisphere, and as discussed already, the influence of the Moon's positive magnetic field.

So, what really changes our weather?

There is one main controlling factor behind all weather patterns. Of course, it is not the only one in what is essentially a chaotic system, but it is the main underlying influence, namely the varying interaction between the Earth's Magnetosphere, the Moon's lesser magnetic field, and the much greater influence of the Sun's Heliosphere together with the constantly changing influences of the planets within our Solar System. A constant that seems to be overlooked is the

fact that the strength of the Earth's Magnetosphere is dominated by the stronger South Pole with its positive (+) magnetic potential force.

The Earth's total magnetic potential is 10-11 Tesla's, and this reacts to the flow of magnetic energy being emitted from the Sun's Heliosphere, to which has a force of 10-4 Tesla. It is the interaction between these two that combines to generate an equilibrium effect out in space some 50,000km above the Earth's surface, and it is this that determines the location and position of planet Earth that sets and controls its orbital position in space. According to Kepler's theory of orbital speeds, such distances therefore have pre-determined relative positions.

Interestingly the Solar Wind speed is 400k/s, taking 99.93 Earth hours from the Sun to reach Earth's surface, while the speed of light travelling at 299,792.5km/s takes only 8 minutes and a few seconds. To complicate matters, there are various spectrum element frequencies, such as radio waves, microwaves, and the like that have magnetism: so all these influences must be considered. All orbital patterns are subject to Kepler's Law, and all are reactive to each other, being subject to all the time of the magnetic influences emitted from the Sun's Corona via., its Heliosphere.

Between the 15th February 2001 to the 22nd December 2012 I monitored barometric pressure patterns over Australia, and discerned an interesting phenomenon that appears to have been overlooked: namely, the seasonal timing of these patterns has altered during this period, and it is clear that there has been an advance of some 30 days in timing during this period (or is it perhaps a retardation?). Either way, this is consistent with changes in the seasonal patterns that have been experienced in Australia since 1998.

One of the more significant observations however has been the changes that have occurred in two respects. The first is in the timing during our Earth year of high and low barometric pressure systems (3); the second is the intensity of these systems. I'm referring to the timings above, but with regards to the other factor of intensity: records show a gradual "flattening out" of the differences between high air pressure and low air pressure systems. This "flattening" is something that has been occurring with a steady consistency since 2012.

Another interesting observation is that during this time the physical locations of the barometric pressure cells have moved further south, away from the locations observed when I first started this monitoring process in 2000. It is quite obvious that any amorphous gas (supposed 'greenhouse' or otherwise) could not drive such a move.

As discussed already, each year the Earth is constantly being subjected to an ongoing sequence of the four variable magnetic polarities being emitted from the Sun's Corona², and these keep moving the Earth in its "Archimede's Screw"-like spiral elliptical orbit, up and over the other side of the Sun. There is a well-recognised phenomenon that demonstrates this pattern: the 'sine wave'. It is the classic illustration of the four magnetic forces at work (Positive/positive(+,+), Positive/negative(+,-), Negative/negative(-,-), and Negative/positive(-,+)) discussed earlier. It is this wave form seen usually in miniature that is the exactly the same in a gigantic form as a result of the interaction with the Sun's Corona. This is illustrated in the Ballerina's Skirt Diagrams,(4) shown below, and the overall effect is called the Sine Wave Flow Effect.

<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interplanetary_Magnetic_Field> and,
<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heliosphere_current_sheet>

Whilst the Earth is orbiting through these four magnetic polarities, the Earth's Magnetosphere reacts as it moves through them, and this is the overwhelming controlling influence over the four seasonal changes each Earth year as experienced in the Earth's two hemispheres, as well as the orbital pattern we experience, daily.

I should make an observation about clouds at this point. The top face of all clouds has a Positive (+) magnetic potential and, conversely, the bottom of all clouds are Negative(-), and so they react to the Earth's Magnetosphere in the control of their heights that is subject to its Barometric environment above the Earth's surface. However, as the Earth changes its orbital position in relation to the Sun's Heliosphere, clouds also demonstrate those changes by longer-term variations in their height above the Earth are also directly associated to the HIGH Barometric Pressures. So not only do these heights reflect regular seasonal changes due to the interaction between the Earth's Magnetosphere and the Sun's Heliosphere, but also the longer-term cycling, because of the Earth's ever-changing position in Space in relation to the Sun's Corona. Again, I must comment that there is no way that any amorphous gas like Carbon Dioxide can ever exercise such control of the Earth's seasons.

At the present moment the clouds above Earth have been higher during our winter period of 2015 when compared to a decade ago, and this reflection of this cyclical change is influenced from the Sun's Corona, because of Earth's position in Space relative to it. As the cycle progresses on in its regular cyclical pattern as discussed, so will the clouds be pushed down to lower levels in the atmosphere that is reflecting a LOW barometric Pressure system. It follows from this observation that rainfall patterns will change over time in line with these height alterations, and also the changes in past, barometric pressures. Currently in Australia, (2015) these Lows are becoming prominent within the whole of this vast continent island and the results for the coming summer seems to again reflect what occurred last summer, Hot days with heavy rain.

The cyclical nature of the changes in not only our year-to-year weather patterns, but also in the varying climatic periods of the regular cycle between "Ice Ages" and "Interglacial" (in which we are at present) simply reflects the overall control of our position in Space relative to the Sun, and to the Sun's varying cyclical position within our Galaxy. It is known now that these cycles are of about 120,000 years duration, and clear evidence of this comes from both Arctic and Antarctic ice core records, among other things. There seems to be little argument against this now, and it is accepted as fact, not fantasy.

On the other hand there has been – and continues to be – a popular movement to ascribe climatic changes not to the cycles discussed, but to the supposed influence of 'greenhouse' gases in the atmosphere, principally Carbon Dioxide (CO₂), being increased vastly because of the effects of burning "fossil fuels" (so called), since the start of the Industrial Revolution and, in particular, from the middle of the 20th Century to date. This popular notion has been promoted by a relatively small group of "experts" supported financially and politically by those who appear to ignore facts, but rather follow fantasy.

The principal fact is that all the records point to one thing: atmospheric CO₂ levels follow temperatures, up or down, and not the other way around by an average of approximately 800 years over a period of 450,000 years. The notion that after millions of years there is a change in this natural behaviour can only be dismissed as fantasy, and in view of the empirical evidence available, those promoting this notion must either be ill-informed or fraudulent.

To move to a larger scale: the Sun, being gaseous, exhibits a particular characteristic which is that its rotation around its Equator is slower than that of its northern and southern hemispheres. Whereas the hemispheres complete a single rotation in 35.5 Earth days, the equatorial region rotates at the speed of only 25 Earth days, with each of the northern and southern sections being at an angle of 18° to its orbital location. What I found was particularly interesting, for by adding these sectors together (i.e., $35.5 \times 2 = 71$ and $25 \times 2 = 50$) amounts to 121.0 Earth days; and when divided by 4 = 30.25 – 0.926987448(6) (my Magnetic constant) = 29.32301255. This interesting number seems to be reflected in many natural phenomena here on Earth, such as coral spawning, Moon phases, human menstrual cycles, and so on.

There are many other features that can be seen and developed in my book: “Climate Change: Explained by Magnetism?” ISBN9780646477220 (2009) [self-published] that reflect and expand on every point made here and more. (5 & 7).

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